

A Survey on Control Design Approaches for Remotely Operated UAVs

Viswa Narayanan Sankaranarayanan*, Sumeet Gajanan Satpute, and George Nikolakopoulos

Abstract—Quadrotors find their roles in various sectors ranging from remote surveillance to autonomous delivery due to their capabilities of hovering, Vertical Take Off and Landing (VTOL) and rapid manoeuvring. They are a viable asset to humans in safety-critical and hazardous operations such as remote inspection and manipulation of tunnels and windmills. These applications induce external disturbances and noises along with the modelling uncertainties in the dynamics. Applications such as aerial manipulation require control from a ground station autonomously or semi-autonomously, which leads to unpredictable delays and lags. In this context, the quadrotor has to perform its goals of following the desired trajectory with minimal deviation and holding its position without any deviation while operating in the environment. So, this article analyses the existing control techniques for the quadrotor tracking problem, which also tackle parametric uncertainties, unknown time-varying delays and ensure safety.

quadrotor, time-varying delays, adaptive control, robust control, unknown uncertainties

I. INTRODUCTION

This survey is aligned towards control of quadrotors in the application of aerial manipulation or surveillance of tunnels, windmills, transmission lines and other constrained spaces, where human presence would be inefficient, hazardous or infeasible. Quadrotors have been potential contenders in transport and surveillance applications in the recent past. The major advantages of a quadrotor such as VTOL and hovering make it a convenient support for humans in hazardous and constrained environments such as working through tunnels, pipelines, aerial inspection etc [1]–[6]. Quadrotors have opened a lot of opportunities in research, especially in control applications owing to their coupled underactuated dynamics.

To set the premise of these applications, let us discuss the desired properties of the aerial manipulator. Size is one of the primary concerns while operating inside a tunnel or when the manipulation takes place on the windmill or transmission lines. The quadrotor must be sufficiently small to perform dexterous operations without colliding with the environment. Identifying and operating in problematic regions demand huge flight time. The constraint on the robot's size necessitates a reduction in the mass of the robot and the power consumption. So, the robot has to carry minimal hardware, including sensors, actuators, power supply and processor.

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All the authors are affiliated to Robotics and AI Team, Department of Computer, Electrical and Space Engineering, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden. Email: (vissan, sumsat, geonik)@ltu.se.

* Corresponding author.

It is obvious that many of the control techniques have been tested and evaluated inside a laboratory or a clear field with a motion capture system (cf. [7], [8]) or a GPS (cf. [9]) based localization. Since the real environments may restrict these convenient methods, visual-inertial sensors (cf. [3]) are inevitable. The current techniques in visual-inertial localization methods require heavy processing capabilities. Since, the intent is to reduce the power consumption and mass of the quadrotor, the processing and control are performed on a ground station (or a remote base station). Further having a remote base station enables a human to teleoperate an aerial manipulator with visual aids. Therefore, the delay in the closed-loop accumulating from communication and processing escalates significantly (cf. [10]). The manipulation environment also introduces additional challenges, such as wind disturbances and contact forces, which if non taken under consideration, are catastrophic to the system's stability (cf. [11]).

Further, modelling such a sophisticated robot's dynamics is almost impossible due to varying payload, external forces (during manipulation), power-draining, actuator's nonlinearity and other factors. Teleoperating an aerial manipulator is impossible when the drone base is subjected to modelling uncertainties and disturbances. In such a case, an adaptive control framework robust to uncertainties and delays and guarantees a predefined accuracy is essential for aerial manipulation. Since the necessary conditions are set, let us look into the schemes for achieving efficient control during an aerial manipulation task.

The rest of the article is divided as it follows. Section II discusses the control techniques that are commonly employed for quadrotors. Section III discusses the existing control schemes for time delayed systems, while Section IV discusses the barrier control approaches for time delays and UAVs, and Section V concludes the article with future considerations.

II. CONTROL TECHNIQUES FOR QUADROTORS

A schematic of the model of a quadrotor is shown in Fig. 1. The quadrotor is modelled using Euler-Lagrangian (EL) dynamics considering its delays and disturbances as shown in (1):

$$m\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{d}_p(t) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_p(t - h(t)) \quad (1a)$$

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}, t)\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, t)\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \mathbf{d}_q(t) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_q(t - h(t)) \quad (1b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_p(t) = \mathbf{R}_B^W(t)\mathbf{U}(t) \quad (1c)$$

Fig. 1. A schematic of quadrotor with coordinate frames.

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1d)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{I_{zz} - I_{yy}}{l} \dot{\theta}(t) \\ \frac{I_{xx} - I_{zz}}{l} \dot{\psi}(t) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{zz} - I_{yy} \dot{\phi}(t) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1e)$$

where m is the total mass of the system; $\mathbf{p}(t) \triangleq [x(t) \ y(t) \ z(t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of the centre of mass of the quadrotor in the Earth-fixed frame at time, t ; $\mathbf{q}(t) \triangleq [\phi(t) \ \theta(t) \ \psi(t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the attitude vector consisting of the roll (ϕ), pitch (θ) and yaw (ψ) angles; $\mathbf{g} \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ mg]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, where g is the acceleration due to gravity in the z -direction; $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}, t) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix with (I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz}) being the inertia along the ${}^B X, {}^B Y, {}^B Z$ axes respectively; $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, t) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the Coriolis matrix and the vectors $\mathbf{d}_p, \mathbf{d}_q \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represent effect of external disturbances (e.g., wind, gust); $h(t)$ is time varying input-delay, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_q \triangleq [u_2(t) \ u_3(t) \ u_4(t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the control inputs for roll, pitch and yaw; $\boldsymbol{\tau}_p(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the generalized control input for position tracking in Earth-fixed frame, with $\mathbf{U}(t) \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ u_1(t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the force vector in the body-fixed frame and $\mathbf{R}_B^W \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ being the $Z - Y - X$ Euler angle rotation matrix describing the rotation from the body-fixed coordinate frame to the Earth-fixed frame, given by:

$$\mathbf{R}_B^W = \begin{bmatrix} c_\psi c_\theta & c_\psi s_\theta s_\phi - s_\psi c_\phi & c_\psi s_\theta c_\phi + s_\psi s_\phi \\ s_\psi c_\theta & s_\psi s_\theta s_\phi + c_\psi c_\phi & s_\psi s_\theta c_\phi - c_\psi s_\phi \\ -s_\theta & s_\phi c_\theta & c_\theta c_\phi \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $c(\cdot), s(\cdot)$ denote $\cos(\cdot), \sin(\cdot)$ respectively. The control inputs are mapped to the rotor velocities using (3).

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_T & C_T & C_T & C_T \\ 0 & lC_T & 0 & -lC_T \\ -lC_T & 0 & lC_T & 0 \\ -C_T C_M & C_T C_M & -C_T C_M & C_T C_M \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_1^2 \\ \omega_2^2 \\ \omega_3^2 \\ \omega_4^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where C_T and C_M are the thrust and moment constants respectively, and l is the arm-length. Though the quadrotor dynamics are nonlinear, they can be simplified into a linear model by taking the small-angle assumptions (cf. [12], [13]) given by (4). This method is popularly used in applying optimization-based control techniques (cf. [14], [15]) and other controllers for linear systems. Such controllers are used in applications where the quadrotor operates near hovering states. We will discuss further how linear systems are controlled even with unknown delays in the following section. Despite their simplicity, the utilization of a linear model in general constraints the quadrotor's manoeuvrability. To make full use of the quadrotor's dexterity, controllers have to be designed considering the complete non-linear dynamics.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x}(t) \\ \ddot{y}(t) \\ \ddot{z}(t) \\ \ddot{\phi}(t) \\ \ddot{\theta}(t) \\ \ddot{\psi}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -g\theta(t) \\ g\phi(t) \\ -g + u_1(t)/m \\ u_2(t)/I_{xx} \\ u_3(t)/I_{yy} \\ u_4(t)/I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

A significant contribution by [16] simplified the control approach of the quadrotor and made the experimental testing feasible. It uses a partly decoupled position and attitude dynamics with a geometric control in the manifold of rotation matrices, which makes it feasible for aggressive manoeuvres. The control schematic proposed by them is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. A schematic of Lee controller [16].

Though the control of quadrotors has been proposed at least a decade back, it is still in the development phase, while most of the proposed controllers require an exact model of the quadrotor dynamics. This is practically infeasible due to the following reasons:

- Since quadrotors are used for a wide range of applications, they come in different shapes and sizes due to the necessary physical components in the quadrotors such as sensors, computer, motors, power supply etc., and varying payloads. Thus, it is almost impossible to identify the dynamics of the quadrotor completely.
- As quadrotors work on outdoor environments, it is necessary to tackle the external disturbances, such as wind.
- There is a considerable difference in functioning of the actuators in real time compared to ideal actuators. Sometimes the actuators might be partly or completely faulty.

- Sensor dependant problems, such as noise and offsets are inevitable.
- There are also problems in communication, such as loss of data, loss of connection, erroneous data and communication lag.

A. Robust and adaptive controllers

The control community have comprehensively covered the challenges caused by parametric uncertainties and external disturbances, while operating a quadrotor. Furthermore, they have proposed various robust and adaptive controllers, whose advantages and disadvantages are discussed in this Section.

The robust control methods [17]–[20] rely on precise knowledge of mass matrix; on the other hand, the adaptive control designs [21]–[28] require a priori knowledge of system structures and of bounds on external disturbances. Such constraints are often difficult to be satisfied in practice due to unknown payload and external disturbances.

To overcome that, researchers have recently applied adaptive sliding mode designs [29]–[32] considering uncertainties to be a priori bounded. However, when such assumption is not satisfied (e.g. state-dependent uncertainty), instability cannot be ruled out (cf. [33], [34]): in the attitude dynamics of a quadrotor, state-dependent uncertainty naturally occurs owing to the Coriolis terms. Crucially, the adaptive control solutions [21], [23], [24], [29] rely on ‘collocated design’ of underactuated systems [34], i.e. these methods only track the actuated coordinates (altitude, roll, pitch and yaw) considering the non-actuated coordinates (lateral (x, y) position) to be stable a priori. However, external disturbances in lateral position may compromise system stability (cf. [34]): a solution to this issue is largely open when disturbances are completely unknown.

The work on [8] proposes an adaptive sliding mode controller for transporting payloads with different masses using a quadrotor while following a desired trajectory. A time-delay control approach for compensating the dynamic uncertainty is proposed in [35]. These controllers require neither a priori knowledge nor the upper bounds of the disturbances.

B. Robustness towards sensor noises

Since most of the works that have taken care of the uncertainty and disturbances have been tested either on an simulated environments or indoors with precise state estimation systems, they mostly do not provide a solution for sensor estimation errors and communication delays. In practical cases, sensors used in laboratory, such as motion capture cameras are infeasible outside the laboratory. For outdoor applications, GPS and inertial feedback are fused for precise state estimation. There are many applications where relying on GPS is impossible. Onboard sensors, such as cameras and IMUs play a major role in state estimation. The same is the problem when a drone is traversing outdoor with obstacles in its path.

A major challenge with these setups are that the sensors are noisy and have other measurement issues. Controllers

such as deploying fusing techniques based on EKF [36] improve the accuracy significantly. There are predictor (cf. [37], observers (cf. [38], [39]) and estimator (cf. [40], [41]) based approaches that have been proposed for taking care of these issues.

The control techniques proposed in this Section take care of uncertainties and noises. However, they do not ensure stability when there is a delay in the closed-loop system. Controllers that specialize on time-delays are discussed in the following section.

III. CONTROL FOR TIME DELAY SYSTEMS

As mentioned earlier, remote operations are heavily affected by delays sourcing from estimation, mapping, planning, controller optimisation, and communication lags. The problem with these delays is that they are highly time-varying owing to communication protocols, the distance between the ground station and the quadrotor, and data loss. When these delays are combined with visual presentation for teleoperation, they become time-varying and unpredictable.

Time delays have posed exciting challenges to the control research. Delays can cause different effects leading to instability in the closed-loop system, depending on how they contribute to the system [42]–[46]. An overview of modelling a delayed system and the methods to control the system are surveyed in these works [45], [47], [48]. The types of modelling of delayed systems using functional differential equations are well described in [47]. The controllers in these surveys are designed using Lyapunov like methods and system model is transformed using state transformation methods [45]. Refined fractional order PID tuning techniques for compensation of time-delays are discussed in [49].

Control approaches for time-delayed systems are broadly classified into linear model and nonlinear model based on the type of the system, they are used in. The following subsections discuss about linear model, nonlinear model and a few control examples for teleoperated systems.

A. Linear model

Towards the control goals in time-delay systems, the simplest form of control approach is by using linear model of the system in discrete form [14], [15], [50]–[53]. The controllers [54], [55] propose solutions for time delays in fuzzy system and chaotic systems. The controllers such as [56] tackle time-delays as well as uncertainty in the dynamics. However, they require a priori knowledge about the system dynamics. To the best knowledge of the author, there hasn’t been any solution proposed for a linear time delay system with no a priori knowledge about the dynamics of the system.

The fundamental approach for continuous linear systems is to use a Smith predictor [57]. However, this approach works only when the model is accurate and the system is stable. There has been several controllers proposed similar to Smith predictor approach that are robust to uncertainties. The controllers that tackle unknown delays are further classified into delay dependant controllers and delay independent controllers (cf. [47], [58]). The delay dependant controllers

require knowledge about the bounds of the time delays. However, they provide a less conservative control compared to time independent controllers.

A robotic system with delays is slightly different from time-delay systems. A time-delay system may include state dynamics depending on the delayed states (cf. [50]–[52]). However, in robotic systems, the state transition does not depend on previous states, instead the measurement that we obtain has a delay, which in turn causes a delay in the control input. Such discretized linear controllers [14], [15] have been implemented and tested on UAVs. However, they can perform only in limited region of operation since linear model of quadrotors use small angle approximation. The controllers mentioned above require exact dynamics of the system and designed only for the attitude dynamics for regulation problems. There is still scope for them to be extended for full-body control similar to [12], [13] with trajectory following problem with uncertain dynamics. Still, it will not solve the problem of aggressive manoeuvring or uncertain inertia.

B. Nonlinear model

Time-delays in nonlinear systems are not well explored. However, to exploit the complete capabilities of a quadrotor, controllers have to use nonlinear dynamics. Several robust and adaptive works have been proposed for nonlinear systems with input delays. In [59] a nonlinear robust controller is proposed for EL systems with time-delay, while [60] proposes a nonlinear adaptive control for the same. The most common application addressed in time delay control of EL system is bilateral control of teleoperated robots and marine robots. In [61], a robust observer based sliding mode controller is proposed for bilateral latency, while an adaptive controller for the same application is proposed in [62] and a robust controller for marine robot with input delay is proposed in [52]. Though these controllers provide solution to input delays, they still require knowledge about the dynamic parameters of the system. There is another class of time-delay control (cf. [35]) that has been tested on various EL systems. Though these controllers work with an input delayed model, they use time-delay only as a feedback to estimate the uncertainties in the dynamics. So, they cannot be deployed for a system with delays.

Furthermore, there are robust controllers [63], [64] and adaptive controllers [65] developed for quadrotors but they are merely adding a static delay to the system. None of these controllers can be used for a remote operation of quadrotors with unknown dynamic uncertainties. So, there is a need to develop a novel control design that involves Euler Lagrangian dynamics of a quadrotor with partly decoupled dynamics as in [16] with no a priori knowledge that would also compensate for communication lags.

C. Control of teleoperated robots

A controller for aerial manipulation is incomplete with a provision for teleoperation. Teleoperation is practiced in underwater robotics, telesurgery and other fields. Involving

Fig. 3. Block diagram of a teleoperated system

a human in the loop simplifies the control pipeline and provides a means for a manual command. Generally, teleoperation is implemented by a bilateral manipulation setup with force feedback (cf. [61], [62]) and visual aid (probably a video relay from the drone’s camera). Addition of the packet loss and the lags in video streaming with the existing factors of distance, connection, and bandwidth of the network results in unpredictable and time-varying closed-loop delays. A block diagram of a time-delayed system is shown in Fig. 3.

Recently, much focus has been given in optimizing the visual aids for the human operator. This line includes visualizing the environment and the manipulator using a predictive 3D display. Predictive enhancements comfort human control. However, it does not ensure the stability of the system. So, robust control techniques have to be implemented to overcome the existing delays in the system.

Lyapunov type controllers are most common in teleoperated systems. They also employ force reflection, passivity based control or impedance representation based on the application. [61] proposes a robust observer-based sliding mode controller for bilateral latency, an adaptive controller for the same application is proposed in [62] and a robust controller for a marine robot with input delay is proposed in [52]. The reference [66] suggests a sliding mode control for the master and impedance control for the slave in a bilateral manipulator system. In [67] a force reflection-based sliding mode controller is proposed, whereas [68] proposes a passivity-based controller. Other types of controllers, such as delay-independent controller [69], predictive controller [70] and event-based controller [71] have also been tested on teleoperated robots. For interested readers, a detailed survey on control of teleoperated systems is provided in [72].

IV. BARRIER CONTROL TECHNIQUES WITH TIME-DELAYS

Safety is one of the main objectives, while operating a quadrotor in a constrained environment. It is achieved by ensuring that the quadrotor’s states, such as position, velocity, orientation, do not violate predefined constraints. It is essential in aerial manipulation in which the quadrotor base has to hold its pose withstanding the reactive forces and disturbances while the manipulator is operating in the environment. The absence of this objective jeopardizes the robot by causing collision and instability. Though the robust and adaptive approaches mentioned in the previous sections may ensure this, they require extensive tuning for different settings and scenarios. These problems give rise to the need for a controller that inherently ensures predefined accuracy and state constraints, while following the tracking problem.

A special type of Lyapunov function called Barrier Lyapunov Function (BLF) is developed for this technique (cf. [73]) that prevents the violation of output constraints. By definition, a BLF applied on a state x , $V(x) \rightarrow \infty$ if $x \rightarrow b$ provided $V(x(t)) \leq r$, $\forall t > 0$, where b is the boundary for the state and r is some positive constant. A typical example of BLF is shown in (5).

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \log \left\{ \frac{x}{b^2 - x^2} \right\} \quad (5)$$

A robust BLF-based backstepping controller is proposed for a quadrotor carrying varying payloads to attain a predefined accuracy in position and attitude tracking is proposed in [74]. BLF based controllers require the initial states to be within the safe sets (or without any violation). However, this can be overcome by using BLFs with time-varying output constraints (cf. [75]).

Over the past decade, theory has been developed to adapt BLF for time delayed systems with the conditions. A few of them are discussed here. [76] proposes a BLF-based controller for input saturation and unknown delays in the system. In [77], a tangent BLF controller is proposed for parametric uncertainties and uncertain time delays. The reference [78], introduces an adaptive controller using BLF with prescribed performance constraint for a space robot with uncertainties, output constraints and input delays. Another common way to tackle parametric uncertainties with time-delays is to design a BLF to overcome uncertainties and use a Krasvoskii or Razhumikhin functional for overcoming delays. An adaptive controller using BLF and Krasvoskii functional is proposed by [79], fuzzy controllers using the same are proposed in [76], [80], [81] and an adaptive fuzzy controller is proposed in [82]. A similar approach with Razhumikhin functional is proposed in [83].

The main disadvantage of BLF based controller is that they are too strong. If the robot violates the barrier due to any reason (actuator non-linearity, sudden gust or communication lag), the Lyapunov value shoots to infinity. Since the states outside the constraints are undefined, there is no way to stabilize the robot. This quality is undesired for systems like quadrotor and it can damage the complete system irreversibly. So, a recent approach of control barrier functions (CBF) (cf. [84]) can be used as a replacement. According to [85], a smooth function $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with its superlevel safe set \mathcal{C} acting on a system $\dot{x} = f(x)$ is said to be a control barrier function if it satisfies the conditions mentioned in (6).

$$\dot{h}(x) \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in \partial \mathcal{C} \quad (6)$$

where $\partial \mathcal{C}$ is the boundary of the safe set \mathcal{C} .

A detailed discussion on how CBFs can be used along with Lyapunov approach for various scenarios involving uncertain environments is shown in [86]. The CBF theory is applied on sampled data with input delays in [87]. It proposes a discrete CBF for systems with known input delays. An approach for dealing with a MIMO systems with partly compensated known delays using CBF is proposed in [88]. A

combination of CBF and control Lyapunov function (CLF) is proposed in [89] for constrained systems with input delays. A similar controller with state predictor is used in [90] for safety-critical control in time-varying delays. A Lyapunov Krasovskii approach for CBF is proposed in [91] to ensure safety and stability in a varying delayed system. It is to be noted that CBF-type controllers have been implemented on the motion planning part and not directly on the actuation level, which is still an open problem for research.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this survey control techniques for time-delayed systems are studied in order to find appropriate approaches for a remotely operated UAV. The controllers are analyzed based on their effectiveness towards parametric uncertainties, time-varying delays and ensuring safety. Based on that, the following open problems are observed:

- Discrete methods are convenient for optimal control and to build a planner along with a model predictive control. So, the linear method with approximation of quadrotor dynamics as mentioned in [14], [15] will be extended to full body dynamics of the quadrotor. Moreover, a control solution will be proposed for input delays and uncertainties in dynamics. Additionally, developing a discrete controller for non-linear systems would support in broadening the scope of operations of the quadrotor.
- Though adaptive controllers such as [60] has been tested for ground robots, they have not been implemented on a quadrotor. Novel ways to saturate the adaptive gains as described in [8], [92] can be exploited for improving the stability of the quadrotors.
- Aerial manipulation has a huge potential for the application of controllers for time delays. However it is still unexplored in this scope. Aerial manipulation also brings up challenges on pre-defined accuracy, where novel adaptive control theories using barrier functions can be developed.
- Aerial manipulation using teleoperation require an intelligent control as to use multilevel control to autonomously stabilise the quadrotor and optimise its pose in order to achieve desired outputs of a teleoperated manipulator. Fault tolerance and intuitive understanding of expected results from a human input can be combined to optimize the planner as well as the low level controller.

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